

Structural, spectral, magnetic and electrochemical studies of μ -chlorobridged copper(II) complexes

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Abstract : Two μ -chlorobridged [(dien)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(dien)](ClO₄)₂ (1), [(PMDT)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(PMDT)](ClO₄)₂ (2), (dien = diethylenetriamine and PMDT = pentamethyldiethylenetriamine) have been synthesized and characterized by using various physico-chemical techniques. Both complexes exhibit subnormal magnetic moment and are involved in antiferromagnetic exchange. The EPR spectra of these complexes are characteristic of a binuclear copper(II) complexes and of axial type. The conproportionation equilibrium constant (K_{con}) for complex 1 was estimated. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity of these compound were also measured.

Keywords : Binuclear copper(II) complexes, EPR spectra, SOD activity.

Introduction

Binuclear μ -halo-bridged copper(II) complexes have attracted much attention as a model for cuproproteins, which contain the same structural units^{1,2}. Binuclear five coordinated copper(II) complexes with monoatomic bridges have been extensively studied^{3,4}, especially those containing halo (chloro or bromo) bridging ligands to develop a correlation between molecular structure and magnetic behaviour. Magneto-structural correlations for this kind of complexes are worthy for constructing molecular based functional materials⁵ and proposing model compounds that mimic the biological active site in copper proteins^{1,2}. Such type of compounds show structures ranging from square pyramid to trigonal pyramid with a variety of bond distance (Cu-X) and bond angles (Cu-X-Cu) resulted in copper(II) dimer units. However, structures of such compounds strongly depends on coordinated environments, such as the nature of the coordinated ligands and the crystal packing for as resulting from the existence of the inter or intramolecular hydrogen bond in the unit cell. This kind of small change in molecular structure can have important effects on the magnetic properties of the complexes⁶. It is also observed that magnetic behaviour of the complexes are influenced by the Cu^I-Cu^{II} separation, Cu-X bond distance and Cu-X-Cu angles formed by the bridging CuX moiety in a Cu₂X dimer

unit. The present paper describes synthesis, magnetic, spectral and electrochemical studies of two μ -chlorobridged [(dien)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(dien)](ClO₄)₂ (1) and [(PMDT)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(PMDT)](ClO₄)₂ (2) complexes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis : Both binuclear complexes were prepared by mixing equimolar CuCl₂·2H₂O and ligand (dien/PMDT) in aqueous solution. The following equation describes the synthesis of the complexes :

where A = dien/PMDT, X = Cl. Both complexes gave satisfactory elemental analysis and further characterized by FAB⁺ mass IR, UV-Vis, EPR and cyclic voltammetry (CV).

Magnetic properties : The magnetic moments of these complexes were collected at ambient temperature. The observed magnetic moment value for binuclear complexes are found to be 1.71 B.M. for complex 1 and 1.73 B.M. for 2. These low values of magnetic moment are indicative of antiferromagnetically coupled complexes ascribed to the paramagnetic species connecting two antiferromagnetically coupled copper(II) ions and attributed to the formation of binuclear complexes⁷.

IR spectra : Infrared spectra of the complexes **1** and **2** exhibit the bands for the organic ligands and counter ions. Particularly complexes a sharp band $\nu(\text{Cu-Cl})$ at 305 cm^{-1} , along with the presence of a band at 165 cm^{-1} (ν_b) indicates the bridging character in the Cu-Cl bond⁸. The strong absorption band at 1100 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{Cl-O})$ and demonstrates the existence as ClO_4^- as counter ion⁹.

EPR spectra : EPR spectra of polycrystalline samples were recorded at room temperature. The spectra of binuclear complexes of the type $\text{Cu} < \begin{smallmatrix} \text{Cl} \\ \text{Cl} \end{smallmatrix} > \text{Cu}$ are characteristic of a binuclear copper complex of axial type¹⁰ ($d_{x^2-y^2}$). The half-field signal ($\Delta Ms = 2$) observed for both complexes, which suggest a magnetic interactions between two copper ions through the $(\mu\text{-chloro})_2$ bridge. Complex **1** shows a broad signal (Fig. 1) with one shallow at high energy (3600 G) yielding $g = 2.127$ whereas the complex **2** shows only a broad signal and yields $g_{\text{iso}} = 2.123$. The variation in peak features in EPR spectra of complex **2** shows that the geometry of the complex in

the solid state is affected by the nature of the coordinating gegenions. This kind of observations may be due to the effect alkylation of the dien ligand. The effect of alkylation of the dien ligand has been to distort the square pyramidal geometry¹⁰ of dien complex partly (with PMDT = pentamethyldiethylenetriamine).

The EPR data indicate a Cu^{II} in geometry in complex **1** that approximates square pyramidal geometry as also proved by single crystal X-ray analysis, however, the exact distortion from this geometry must be some what difficult than in complex **2** as evidenced by the difference in zero-field content in the EPR spectra. Also in spectrum of complex **1** a broad hump at 3600 G is appeared. EPR spectrum in polycrystalline state for complexes **2** shows that the Cu^{II} coordination geometry is that of a more distorted square pyramid in which steric interactions of the methyl groups cause a distortion from the basal plane.

The solution EPR spectra for both complexes were recorded in 100% DMSO solution at 77 K. The spectra

Fig. 1. X-band EPR spectrum (RT) of the polycrystalline $[(\text{dien})\text{Cu}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}(\text{dien})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**).

are shown in Fig. 2. The anisotropic g values for complexes **1** and **2** were well resolved, showing a typical axial symmetry. The EPR spectra of frozen solution for both complexes exhibited well defined hyperfine structure with parallel (g_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (g_{\perp}). In spectrum of complex **1** a high field shallow (3390 G) is appeared. This high field shallow is indicative of Cu-Cu bridged system¹¹. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ cm ratio for these complexes comes out to be 150 cm for **1** and 165 for **2** indicating a rather square pyramidal geometry with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. These spectral and for **1** is very similar to that of Cu-Zn SOD having $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ cm⁻¹ of 165 cm¹¹ for which an arrangement around the copper ion intermediate between a trigonal pyramidal and a square pyramidal has been suggested. On the basis of above aforementioned observations, in solution bis μ -chlorobridge breaks according to eq. (2).

This observation is similar to the bridge breaking

behaviour of other reported binuclear complexes¹².

UV-Vis spectra : UV-Vis spectra were recorded in solid state and in solution. The visible spectra, in the solid state, of complexes **1** and **2** display a band at 650 nm and 700 nm respectively. These spectra have one shoulder \sim 1000 nm. The UV-Visible absorption spectra for penta-coordinated copper(II) complexes usually fall into two categories¹³. Square pyramidal complexes typically show a high energy absorption band in the visible region with a low energy shoulder. In contrast, trigonal bipyramidal complexes have a low energy absorption band with a high energy shoulder in the visible region¹³. Therefore, these complexes show spectral features of square pyramidal geometry, which suggest that it is the geometric arrangement adopted by the Cu^{II} center in these complexes in the solid states. This is in agreement with X-ray analysis for complex **1**, where a distorted square pyramidal geometry was observed, as discussed above. The low energy band may also be attributed due to coupling of two copper centers. In DMF solution complex **1** show a

Fig. 2. X-band EPR spectra of [(dien)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(dien)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**) and [(PMDT)Cu(μ -Cl)₂Cu(PMDT)](ClO₄)₂ (**2**).

high energy band at 650 nm and low energy band at ~1000 nm. The high energy band in CH₂Cl₂ undergoes a red shift (690 nm), attributable to solvolysis whereas low energy band invariant in this complex. Therefore geometry of **1**, in these solvents remains square pyramidal, as observed in solid state. In solutions complex **2** shows only a broad band at 690 nm. This behavior is characteristic of tetragonally distorted octahedral complex and suggests that solvent molecules occupy the vacancy positions in the first metal coordination spheres, when the complex is dissolved in solvent. Complex **1** and **2** showed two additional peaks at ~300 nm and ~480 nm. The peak at ~300 nm is attributable to intraligand transition whereas peak at ~480 nm is attributable to a ligand to metal transfer transition¹⁴.

Electrochemistry : The electrochemical behaviour of complex is **1** and **2** were recorded in DMSO solution under an inert atmosphere, with NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte in the potential range +1.2 to -1.2 V vs SCE. The CV of **1** is characterized by two successive, one electron quasi-reversible electrochemical process (Fig. 3). The first $E_{1/2}$ (0.468 V) can be assigned to a Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}/Cu^I-Cu^I redox couple and the second $E_{1/2}$ (-0.34 V) cor-

responds to a subsequent Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}/Cu^I-Cu^I redox process¹⁵. The extra peak beyond the second reduction may result from adsorption of the mixed-valence form to the electrode surface or possibly further reduction of the dicopper(I) form to Cu⁰¹⁶. The conproportionation constant (K_{con}) for the formation of the Cu^{II}/Cu^I mixed valence complex,

$$E^1_{1/2} - E^2_{1/2} = 0.0591 \log K_{con} \quad (6)$$

was determined to be 4.7×10^{13} . The magnitude of K_{con} for complex **1** can be compared to the values for several well characterized, symmetric ruthenium systems¹⁷ with K_{con} equal to $\sim 3.2 \times 10^{11}$, 6.49×10^{20} . Whereas CV of complex **2** in DMSO shows a single irreversible reduction wave at -0.735 V which can attributed to Cu^{II}-Cu^I redox process and this observation is in support of UV-Vis findings.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of [(dien)Cu(μ-Cl)₂Cu(dien)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**).

SOD activity : The SOD activity of complexes 1 and 2 were assayed¹⁸ by the use of alkaline DMSO as a source of O_2^- in association with nitrobluetetrazolium chloride as a scavenger of O_2^- . The complexes in the present study exhibit catalytic activity towards the dismutation of O_2^- . Complex 1 and 2 showed less activity ($IC_{50} = 14$ for 1 and $21 \mu M$ for 2) than the native enzyme ($0.04 \mu M$). This reduced activity may be due to the strong ligand field created by the used tridentate ligands (i.e. dien and PMDT), which oppose the interaction of the complexed copper with O_2^- . PMDT exerts stronger field than dien hence complex 2 is less active than complex 1. In these complexes, copper(II) is coordinated with 3N and 2Cl atoms to give distorted square pyramidal geometry. The distortion of these complexes favour the geometrical change, which is essential for the catalysis as the geometry of copper in the SOD enzyme also changes from distorted square pyramidal¹⁹.

Experimental

Materials : Copper chloride dihydrate (S.d. fine-Chemical), dien and PMDT (Aldrich) were used as received. Other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Copper(II) chloride dihydrate was purchased from S.d. fine-Chemicals, India. All other chemicals used were of synthetic grade and used as received. FAB (fast atomic bombardment) mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 Mass Spectrometer using xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature (RT) with *m*-nitrobenzoyl alcohol as the matrix. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Gouy balance using a mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units). Diamagnetic corrections were estimated from Pascal Tables. The ligand field spectra were recorded at $25^\circ C$ on a Shimadzu UV-Visible recording Spectrophotometer UV-1601 in solution. IR-spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. X-band EPR spectra were recorded on Varian E-line Century Series Spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at the X-band (~ 9.4 GHz) with 100 kHz modulation frequency. TCNE was used as field

marker. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a Bioanalytical System BAS-100 electrochemical analyzer. The cell was a standard three electrode system with a platinum working electrode a platinum wire auxiliary and a silver/silver chloride the counter electrode. The measurements were performed at room temperature in DMSO containing $0.1 M$ $NaClO_4$. The solution was deoxygenated by purging nitrogen gas. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of super oxide radical (O_2^-) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O_2^- scavenger¹⁸. In general, $400 \mu l$ sample to be assayed was added to a solution containing $2.1 ml$ of $0.2 M$ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and $1 ml$ of $56 \mu M$ of alkaline DMSO solution was added while stirring. The absorbance was then monitored at $540 nm$ against a sample prepared under similar condition except NaOH was absent in DMSO. A unit of SOD activity is the concentration of complex, which causes 50% inhibition of alkaline DMSO mediated reduction of nitro blue tetrazolium chloride (NBT).

A mixture of $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($0.340 g$, $2 mmol$) and dien ($0.206 g$, $2 mmol$) in water ($50 ml$) was stirred for $1 h$. An aqueous solution of $NaClO_4$ ($0.367 g$, $3 mmol$) was added to above reaction mixture and continued the stirring for $1 h$ more. The resulting solution was filtered to remove any undissolved particles. After staying for few days, dark blue crystals were collected from desiccator. Yield 55% (Found : C, 15.96 ; H, 4.37 ; N, 13.91 . Calcd. for $Cu_2C_8H_{26}N_6Cl_4O_8$: C, 15.93 , H, 4.34 ; N, 13.92%).

A sample of the PMDT complex $[(PMDT)Cu(\mu-Cl)_2Cu(PMDT)](ClO_4)_2 (2)$ was prepared according to the above procedure used for the dien complex 1, using PMDT instead of dien. Yield 60% (Found : C, 29.11 ; H, 6.21 ; N, 11.27 . Calcd. for $Cu_2C_{18}H_{46}N_6Cl_4O_8$: C, 29.07 ; H, 6.19 ; N, 11.30%).

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